

ULTRADRAWING OF NANODIAMOND REINFORCED POLY (VINYL ALCOHOL) NANOCOMPOSITE FIBER

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ABSTRACT

As a new member of nanocarbons, nanodiamond (ND) has recently been exploited in the fields of nanotechnology. ND consists of core shell structure; the core of diamond primary particles and the shell of graphite like layer with oxygen containing functional groups. The core provides high performances derived from diamond, such as high bulk modulus, high thermal conductivity, hardness, wear resistance and so on. Unlike the conventional nanocarbons, ND can be nano-dispersed in water due to the oxygen containing functional groups on the surface. Previously, we reported that ND was highly dispersed in poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) matrix by using water as a processing medium. As a result, ND was found to show excellent reinforcement effects on the nanocomposite performances. In this study, ND reinforced PVA nanocomposite fibers were prepared through gel process. The structure and the properties of the nanocomposite fibers were investigated. The orientation degree of PVA crystallites increased with increasing of DR and achieved around 97 % for both PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. Since PVA crystallites were highly oriented, the mechanical properties of the fibers increased by ultradrawing. As for the nanocomposite fibers, remarkable increase in the Young's modulus and the tensile strength were observed. For example, the PVA/ND nanocomposite fiber with 1 wt % ND loading showed the increase in the tensile strength from 0.05 MPa (DR=1) to 1.89 GPa (DR=50). Surprisingly, the Young's modulus was revealed to be 67 GPa at DR of 50, which approaches to the value of glass fiber (~70 GPa). It was suggested that the excellent reinforcement effect of ND was exploited in the nanocomposite fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Along with the expansion of the nanotechnology, nanocarbons, such as carbon nanotubes, have attracted a great deal of attention. It has been revealed that nanocarbons show outstanding performances such as high mechanical properties and unique electrical properties. Nanocarbons have been extensively investigated as promising reinforcements for polymer nanocomposites [1, 2]. Enormous amount of research were conducted and various polymer/nanocarbon nanocomposites, such as films [3-8] and fibers [9-13], were developed.

Nanodiamond (ND) is a new member of nanocarbons which has recently been exploited in the fields of nanotechnology. Nowadays, ND with the size of less than 10 nm has been produced by several different procedures; detonation technique, chemical vapor deposition, ion irradiation of

graphite, high pressure-high temperature, shock wave and so on [2]. There are growing demands for the application of ND, including nanocomposite, optical and biomedical fields. ND consists of characteristic structure of core shell structure. Due to the core of diamond primary particles, ND shows high performances derived from diamond such as high bulk modulus, high thermal conductivity, hardness, wear resistance and so on. The shell is composed of graphite like layer with oxygen containing functional groups. These groups enable ND to be highly dispersed in water. In addition, these groups can be the initiation site for various modifications.

So far, in order to obtain the preferable interaction between ND and polymer matrices, various kinds of functionalization of ND was conducted [14-16]. Remarkable increase in the mechanical properties by the incorporation of functionalized ND was reported by Mochalin *et al.* [17]. They prepared amino-functionalized ND by using ethylenediamine. The covalently bonded nanocomposites were produced by the incorporation of amino-functionalized ND into epoxy resin. It was revealed that the Young's modulus was increased one order of magnitude by the incorporation of 7 wt % of amino-functionalized ND. Afterward, they adjusted the amount of amino group of the amino-functionalized ND and the filler content in the aim of maximizing the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite [18]. They showed that the interaction between the interface between ND and epoxy resin as well as the dispersibility of ND were important factor for the performance of the nanocomposites.

In our previous report, we prepared ND reinforced polymer nanocomposite using poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) as a matrix. It was revealed that ND was highly dispersed in PVA matrix by using water as a processing medium [4]. The PVA/ND nanocomposites showed remarkable increase in the mechanical properties and the thermal properties. For example, the Young's modulus of the nanocomposites in particular increased 2.5 times compared with that of PVA film with only 1 wt % ND loading. Due to the hydrogen bonding of oxygen containing functional groups on ND surface, the strong interaction arose between ND and PVA. In addition, since ND was highly dispersed in PVA matrix, the high optical transparency of PVA was successfully maintained for the nanocomposites.

In this study, ND reinforced PVA nanocomposite fibers were prepared through gel process. The gel fibers were prepared in the glass tube followed by the drawing at 150°C up to the draw ratio (DR) of 50. The effect of drawing on the structure and the properties of the nanocomposite fibers were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

PVA powder (Poval-145) was kindly supplied by Kuraray Co. Ltd. The degree of polymerization and the degree of saponification was 4500 and 98–99 %, respectively. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was purchased from Wako Chemical Industry Ltd. ND aqueous suspension with the ND content of 2.75 wt % was supplied from Bando Chem. Ind. ND powder was synthesized by detonation method. A mixture of 2,4,6-trinitrotoluene and trimethyltrinitramine (explosive) was detonated under an inert atmosphere. The detonation soot was purified by strong acids, such as permanganic acid, nitric acid and sulfuric acid, and then annealed. The ND aqueous suspension was obtained by rinsing the powder by pure water and dispersed by wet milling process in bead mill. All the materials were used as received.

2.2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

ND aqueous suspension was diluted with distilled water and was mixed with DMSO (DMSO/distilled water = 80/20). PVA powder was added to the suspension and dissolved at 90°C. The concentration of PVA in the suspension was 10 wt %. ND content was adjusted to be 1 wt % against PVA. The PVA/ND suspension was vigorously stirred and sealed in a glass tube. After cooling at -20°C for 24 h, the PVA/ND gel fiber was taken out from the tube and soaked in ethanol for 12 h. The gel fiber was dried at room temperature, followed by vacuum drying at 40°C for 48 h. Subsequently, the fiber was drawn in an oven at 150 °C. The draw ratio (DR) was ranged from 1 (undrawn) to 50.

2.3 CHARACTERIZATION

The diameter of the fibers was measured using optical microscope (OPTIPHOT2-POL, Nikon Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). X-ray diffraction was performed using an X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku, RINT2100) equipped with Ni-filtered CuK α radiation at 40 kV and 20 mA. The 2θ scan data were collected at 0.02 degree intervals at a scanning speed of 1.0 degree/min. X-ray diffraction images were taken and the azimuthal intensity distribution graph for the 101/10 $\bar{1}$ reflection of PVA was obtained. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) was measured from the graph and the degree of orientation (π) of PVA crystallites was calculated by the following equation (1):

$$\pi = \frac{180 - \text{FWHM}}{180} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The mechanical properties were measured by tensile test using Autograph AGS-1kND (Shimadzu Co., Kyoto, Japan). The cross head speed of 2 mm/min and the initial length was 20 mm. More than 10 specimens were tested for each sample.

3 RESULTS

3.1 STRUCTURE

Figure 1 shows optical images of (A) undrawn and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. The diameter of the fibers decreased from 348 μm to 64 μm by the drawing. The similar decrease in the diameter was observed for the PVA fibers. This indicates that the polymer chain was strained and oriented along the drawn direction.

Figure1: Optical images of (A) undrawn and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers.

Figure 2 shows the X-ray diffraction images of (A) undrawn (DR=1) and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. The most intensive reflection was the 101/10 $\bar{1}$ reflection of PVA. The reflection appeared as a homogeneous Debye-Scherrer ring for the undrawn fiber. This indicates that PVA crystallites were randomly oriented in the undrawn fiber. On the other hand, the reflection was highly focused on the equatorial direction for the drawn fiber. The PVA crystallites were highly oriented parallel to the drawn direction by the uniaxial drawing. In order to calculate the degree of orientation of PVA crystallites, the azimuthal intensity distribution for the 101/10 $\bar{1}$ reflection was obtained from the X-ray diffraction images.

Figure 3 shows the azimuthal intensity distribution for the 101/10 $\bar{1}$ reflection of (A) undrawn and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. $I(\Phi)$ is the intensity along the Debye-Scherrer ring and Φ is the azimuthal angle. The base angle of $\Phi=0$ was inserted in Figure 2. The homogeneous Debye-Scherrer ring of the undrawn fiber was presented as a broad profile. In contrast, the intensity peak appeared for the drawn fiber. The degree of orientation of PVA crystallites was calculated by using equation (1). The degree of orientation for the PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers as a function of DR was shown in Figure 4. It was revealed that the degree of orientation increased from 18 % to 98 % by the drawing of the PVA/ND nanocomposite fiber to the DR of 50. The degree of orientation largely increased at DR of 10 for both PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. In

the range of the high DR, the degree of orientation of PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers was found to be slightly higher than that of PVA fibers. In our previous report, we revealed that the ND particles had large effect on the amorphous region rather than crystalline region [4]. It was assumed that the further enhancement of the orientation degree was attributed to the effect of the ND particles on the amorphous region of PVA in the PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers.

Figure 2: X-ray diffraction images of (A) undrawn (DR=1) and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers.

Figure 3: Azimuthal intensity distributions of the equatorial reflection (101/10ī) for (A) undrawn (DR=1) and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA/ND nanocomposite fiber.

Figure 4: Degree of orientation of PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers.

3.2 PROPERTIES

Figure 5 shows the stress-strain curves of (A) undrawn (DR=1) and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. It was obvious that the tensile strength and the Young's modulus of the nanocomposite fibers were much higher than those of PVA fibers for both undrawn and drawn fibers.

As for the undrawn fibers, the Young's modulus increased from 2.7 GPa to 4.2 GPa with only 1 wt % ND loading. Furthermore, as for the drawn fibers, the Young's modulus of the nanocomposite fiber was found to be 1.7 times higher than that of PVA fiber. In our previous report, we revealed remarkable increase in the mechanical properties as well as thermal properties of the PVA/ND nanocomposite film [4]. The Young's modulus of nanocomposite film with 1 wt % ND loading was 2.5 times higher than that of PVA film. It was shown that the effective stress transfer was achieved also for the nanocomposite fibers due to the favourable interaction between PVA and ND.

Interestingly, the elongation at break of the drawn nanocomposite fiber was almost the same as that of PVA fiber, while the Young's modulus and the tensile strength were much higher. Previously, we conducted uniaxial drawing of the PVA/graphene oxide nanocomposite. The nanocomposite was drawn to DR of 3. It was revealed that elongation at break of drawn nanocomposite was increased by the drawing. Generally, the initial crack is often caused at the interface between filler and matrix due to the high stress concentration at the filler edges [19]. It was reported that the highly aligned GO reduced the stress concentration, in addition, hindered the crack propagation in the drawn nanocomposite [20]. However, unlike graphene oxide, ND has low aspect ratio. Therefore, it is unlikely to reduce the stress concentration by the alignment. It was assumed that the arrangement of ND in the highly oriented PVA crystallites played an important role in the elongation behaviour of the drawn nanocomposite fiber.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curves of (A) undrawn (DR=1) and (B) drawn (DR=50) PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers.

Figure 6 shows the (A) Young's modulus and (B) tensile strength of PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers as a function of DR. Both the Young's modulus and the tensile strength increased with the increasing of DR. At DR of 40 and 50, the Young's modulus and the tensile strength of the nanocomposite fibers largely increased while those of the PVA fiber tended to saturate. As previously mentioned, the excellent reinforcement effect was imparted to the nanocomposite fibers due to the effective stress transfer. However, it was assumed that there were other reasons to enhance the mechanical properties of the drawn nanocomposite fibers.

From the X-ray diffraction, it was revealed that the degree of orientation of PVA crystallites in the PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers was higher than that of PVA fibers. Furthermore, from the differential scanning calorimetry measurement, the crystallinity of the drawn nanocomposite fiber was found to be

higher than that of drawn PVA fiber. This suggested that the interfacial crystallization [21] was occurred in the nanocomposite fibers. These highly crystallized and highly oriented PVA regions are expected to bring the remarkable increase in the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite fibers.

Figure 6: (A) Young's modulus and (B) tensile strength of PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The simple, cheap and environmentally friendly method of gel preparation was developed. The PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers were prepared through gel process followed by drawing. The degree of orientation increased with the increasing of DR for both PVA fibers and PVA/ND nanocomposite fibers. At DR of 50, the degree of orientation of the nanocomposite fiber was 98 %, indicating that PVA crystallites were oriented almost parallel to the drawn direction. It was found that the degree of orientation was enhanced by the presence of ND. The remarkable increase in the mechanical properties was revealed for the nanocomposite fibers by the drawing. The Young's modulus of the drawn PVA/ND nanocomposite fiber with DR of 50 was found to be 68 GPa, which approaches to the value of glass fiber. It was shown that ND exerted the excellent reinforcement effect on the drawn nanocomposite fibers. Further investigation on the alignment of the filler will contribute to the further improvement of the mechanical properties. This unique technique of nanocomposite fiber preparation will provide a new approach for the development of the nanocarbon reinforced polymer nanocomposite fibers and would broaden the applicability of these materials.

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